

SCHEDULING OPTIMIZATION USING PERT AND CRASHING METHOD IN AIRCRAFT MANUFACTURER

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Abstract

Aircraft manufacturing industry is one of promising industry in Indonesia. PT X as one of the aircraft manufacturing company had some problems during the final assembly proses in the second station that leads to the delayed completion of product Plane NX-2nd Phase. Therefore, the purpose of this study was to identify which activities were subjected to time reduction based on the company discretion. Initially, the completion time rate of the final assembly in the Station 2 was 14 days, equals to 98 hours. Based on the discretion of the company, this station was regenerated using crashing with the consideration on the critical path which had been elicited by PERT method. It could be inferred from the result, the critical paths were in operation 2, 7, 9, 14, 16 and 22. Therefore, these operations were targeted on performing the crashing. Furthermore, the results showed the crashing score reduced from 14 days into 10 days (70 hours) with a probability value of 48.08%. In addition, and for consideration, company that continued to apply crashing on the operation 22 (as the subsequent of critical path) would resulted in the escalation of the cost slope into 4.8%.

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1. INTRODUCTION

X Company is a reputable aircraft manufacturing industry in Indonesia. The company was founded in 1976. It focused on design skills, development, building components, and aircraft assembly for civilian and military requirements. Related to this study, N-X aircraft manufacture was in the stage of "The 2nd Product Development (PD-2)". A year ago, the aircraft took to the sky for a twenty-hour test flight. A problem faced by the company was that they could not do the final assembly process of the N-X PD-2 aircraft in the 2nd Station. The 2nd Station was a station in which avionic system is installed. The assembly process delayed that it caused duration overrun. The project could not be finished on time as it was planned. Several factors that affected the project delay were materials, human resources, method of production system, and environment. Therefore, company needed to arrange strategic planning and scheduling to complete the project on time.

Running a project in a limited time required a good plan so that it will not cause cost overrun on resources, materials, and scheduling management. In this case, the leader of the project should figure out how to accelerate the project completion so that the project could be finished on time or even earlier to avoid cost increase because it could also boost the company's performance in the future. This study was undertaken in 2017 in Indonesia. Statistics and information about circumstances of the area was gained from direct observation and interviews. The ones interviewed were people joined in a production-planning department of the company. The production planning system of the aircraft company employed project management due to complexity of technology. The project management helped the researchers in observing the company's problems. To overcome project delay, strategic planning needed to be arranged

carefully. The problem of N-X PD-2 aircraft final assembly delay required effective strategic planning of the final assembly in the 2nd Station. Analyzing the cause of project delay using cause and effect diagram could solve the problem.

Determining new track after crashing using Program Evaluation and Review Technique (PERT) could help to shorten the project duration as its normal time. A previous study done by (1) was about the minimization of pessimistic time in PERT network by pouring more money to accelerate the activities in critical path. (2) undertook a research on maximizing possibility to complete project on time using limited resources of Pert-Type Network (PTN). Calculating additional cost after crashing needs to be considered by managers to take any further decisions. It is expected that this study can solve the problems of manufacturing N-X PD-2 aircraft in X Company. It is also expected that this analysis can help the company to reduce project cost. A previous study done by (3) showed that the use of PERT method was applied to provide specific duration followed the CPM that was used to give special attention to tasks that fell under critical path. The model resulted from the study was a strong equipment to help manufacturing managers and supervisors to make optimum decisions in estimated time for completion, scheduling, budgeting, key action and earlier completion with minimum time-consuming. Another research by (4) showed that PERT was used to provide deterministic and probabilistic aspects that were applied in planning, scheduling, controlling duration, and calculating project cost. Thus, the parking project scheduling using PERT method will adapt easier towards project activities change by managing project delay and cost efficiently. Moreover, results of a study performed by (5) explained that PERT could give a great contribution to time and cost optimization of horizontal laminator project. Production processes that were applied to industrial project could reduce cost and even increase the number of performed projects with a consequence of leading the increasing competitiveness.

The other research undertaken by (6) used Petri Nets Based Approach. The result suggested that the approach enabled project managers to consider not only about resources but also various types of variables or obstacles relating to projects, such as activity cost. Each of the variables could also be considered as fuzzy variables. A result of another previous research done by (7) showed that CPM and PERT are useful for optimizing time schedule of each of construction project. The complexity of this model is increased when there are more activities to be performed with fairly complicated precedence relationship. On the other hand, providing less network diagram than dummy activities increase duration. Probabilistic model is more likely suitable for construction company because activity durations is estimated based on labor, material, and other circumstances. Another research by (8) displayed an analysis using Critical Path Method (CPM) and Program Evaluation and Review Technique (PERT) for Project Planning. This study focused on how network diagram was mapped based on project activities lists and estimations that are involved in each method. This project consists of example problems, along with the complex problems that were built in the beginning, using CPM and PERT. The other study performed by (9) investigated planning project. The study tried to add several new aspects to this subject. It was examined by a number of project samples on how different distributions of practice affect the result if it is compared to the use of beta distribution in PERT. Both of dummy project and real life project showed that +/- 10% difference in PERT three-point estimation concept caused greater deviations than application of different activity distribution.

2. Methods

2.1. Cause and Effect Diagram

Cause and effect diagram is a diagram that describes lines and symbols that shows the relationship between the cause and effect of a problem, which is then carried out to take further corrective action on the problem (10) Cause and effect diagram or causal diagram is a tool used to identify, sort and display various possible causes, or certain quality characteristics. At this time, X

Company is observing a problem caused by a delay in the final assembly process, which causes delays at the time of planned project's completion.

2.2. Load Leveling

Load leveling is an allocation of work in a certain time or operation's rescheduling, so that a certain amount of work that has to be completed in a specific time can be distributed evenly and also achievable (11). In other words, load leveling is a distribution of workloads to a number of equipment/machines or workers with the aim that the work can be evenly distributed between one and another work center. Considering the limited number of workers, work areas and equipment/machines, load leveling can be done. So, it can optimize the existing resources and also complete a number of works in accordance with the specified time.

2.3. Program Evaluation and Review Technique (PERT)

In project management, there is an analytical technique used in planning, scheduling and monitoring, which is Program Evaluation and Review Technique (PERT), pert is the ability to put an uncertainty toward estimated completion time of activities on certain types of projects (1). PERT is a method designed to assist the project planning, scheduling and also project control (2). In PERT, the emphasis is placed on activities that get the most accurate period. The solution to solve the problems is three estimation times; optimistic (a), realistic (m), and pessimistic (b) (12).

2.4. Crashing

There are many ways to complete a project with less than the normal time. One of them can be achieved by using crashing approach. Crashing approach begins by determining the estimated time-cost slope for each activity. Cost slope is a cost measurement for shortening the duration of an activity. The calculation of the cost slope is as follows: (9)

$$\text{Cost Slope} = \frac{C_c - C_n}{T_n - T_c} \quad (1)$$

where:

C_c = Normal cost

C_n = Crash cost

T_n = Normal time

T_c = Crash time

In applying additional resources, either adding workers or overtime in order to reduce the duration of the critical path can use the following methods:

1. The addition of resources must be applied to critical path activities and also on non-critical lane that have a nearly same length of duration with the critical path. Resources that can be channeled to other activities must be taken from activities that have the largest slack (10).
2. The addition of resources must be applied initially to activities that have the smallest cost slope. This will minimize the cost of reducing the duration of the project.
3. The addition of resources must be applied to activities that require earlier time in project completion. According to Almahdy (2008), if wanting a faster settlement time with the same scope, then the resource needs will increase. This source can be in form of labor, material, equipment, or other forms that can be stated as a number of funds (11). These sources may include labor, material, equipment, or other forms that can be stated as a number of funds.

3. Results and Discussion

3.1. Load Leveling and Allocation Resources

The specifications of the workers needed in the final assembly line (FAL) at Station 2 of the N-X PD-2 aircraft are divided into three specifications namely FMI (Mechanic Instalation), FAI (Electrical Instalation), XSE (Sealent). While the work area is divided into four areas namely OF (Outer fuselage), FF (Fuslage Forward), ACF (After Center fuslage), Sealent.

In the project work, equalization was carried out in determining the workload in each work operation and also allocation of resources for labor and maximum capacity of the workplace. In the final assembly schedule of post 2, the sorting was grouped according to the operating time of each work area, which are FF, OF, ACF and Sealant area. The worker's number of specifications in each operation depended on the capacity of the work area where the workers working on. In general, the number of FMI manpower specifications in the work area of OF, FF and ACF usually done by 3 manpower that were decided based on capacities of each work area. In addition, the number of FAI manpower's specifications in the OF, FF or ACF work area were usually 2 by considering the capacity in each work area. Whereas in Figure 1 is a workload graph on the final assembly line (FAL). In this study using Ms. software. Project 2013.

Based on Figure 1, it can be seen that the higher workload was in the work area of ACF because, in that area, there are some assembly operation of electrical installation. The installation was done in fuselage that it caused high workload in terms of its four-worker capacity in that area. Meanwhile, in the FF and OF area, there was no high workload because the job was done at the outside area and front part of the aircraft. After observing workload and maximum capacity in each work area, the maximum number of workers who could be employed for the final assembly of the aircraft can be concluded. The figure 2 shows the allocation human resources for FMI is 6 workers, FAI is 2 workers, and allocation for XSE is 1 worker. The number of the workers concluded based on the workload in every work area and its maximum worker capacity.

Figure 1. Load Leveling

Figure 2. Resource Allocation

PT X set salary regulation for hours of work and overtime pay. The regulation did not distinguish workers based on the specification of N-X PD-2 aircraft final assembly at the 2nd Station. The following are salary based on normal cost is IDR 30.000 wage/hour and overtime cost is IDR 35.000 wage/hour.

3.2. Cause and Effect Diagram

First step to take in formulating problems at PT X was mapping all the causes using fishbone diagram. The Figure 3 shows problems and its causes. It was discovered that there were two main causes of project delay and data delay of human resources. The problems needed a good scheduling in the process of final assembly line (FAL) at the 2nd station. One of the solutions to this kind of problem is applying PERT in the final assembly process.

Figure 3. Cause and Effect Problem

3.3. Program Evaluation and Review Technique (PERT)

There were some steps of operation in the process of Final Aircraft Line (FAL). There were 29 activities that were performed step-by-step, the detailed information is displayed in the Table 1. Based on the process of N-X PD-2 aircraft final assembly at the 2nd Station, the sequence of activities is provided in the Figure 4.

Figure 4. Network Diagram of N-X PD-2 Aircraft

The red-colored Operation is a critical path in the process of aircraft final assembly at the 2nd station, operation 2, operation 7, operation 9, operation 14, operation 16 and operation 22. This operation consists of the result of duration shortening that has been decided by the company. The critical path could be determined after calculating forward and backward pass based on ES, EL, LS, and LF values in each activities of final aircraft line (FAL) at the 2nd Station. By doing this calculation, the activities included in critical path and activities included in non-critical path can be seen. The critical path itself is an operation in which delay can be possibly performed, if the slack time value is 0. The result of critical path in the final aircraft line at station 2 is displayed in the Table 1. There are three estimation times that are used in the calculation using PERT, namely: optimistic time, realistic time, and pessimistic time. These times was directly taken from employees and final N-X aircraft assembly planning. Besides, data of times and result of estimation of T_e and V value are displayed on the Table 1. The result of V value (variance) is 89 hours. If it was analyzed using z table, its probability could be calculated by including uncertainty in completing the 2nd Station of final aircraft assembly process, the value is 0.4808 or 48.08% using the following equation. The Table 1 shows that the final assembly path has 6 critical paths in activities: 2 (install of B), 7 (install of G), 9 (Install I), 14 (connection N), 16 (install of P), and 22 (installation of V).

Table 1. Expected Time PERT

No	Task Name	Optimistic	Mostlikely Time	Pessimistic	Duration (Te)	Variance (V)	Critical	Predecessors	Successors
1	Install A	3	4	7	4	2.0	-	-	30
2	Install of B	2	2	4	2	1.4	Yes	-	8
3	Install C	2	3	5	3	1.7	-	18	19
4	Install D	2	3	5	3	1.7	-	18	19
5	Install of E	3	4	7	4	2.0	-	-	16
6	Install of F	1	2	7	2	1.4	-	-	9
7	Instal of G	4	5	8	5	2.2	Yes	3	10
8	Install of H	3	4	6	4	2.0	-	7	-
9	Install of I	4	5	7	5	2.2	Yes	8	17
10	Install of J	3	3	14	3	1.7	-	-	13
11	Install of K	4	5	7	5	2.2	-	14	-
12	Install of L	5	7	7	7	2.6	-	11	-
13	Install of M	5	6	7	6	2.4	-	-	12
14	Connection N	9	10	15	15	3.9	Yes	27;20;19;23	-
15	Install of O	5	5	6.5	5	2.2	-	6	22
16	Install P	1	1	7	1	1.0	Yes	10	23
17	Mixing Q	2	2	3	2	1.4	-	-	4;5
18	Install of R	5	6	8	6	2.4	-	4;5	15
19	Install of S	19	20	35	20	4.5	-	-	30;27FF;15
20	Install of T	9	10	12	10	3.2	-	22	26
21	U charging system	4	5	7	5	2.2	-	16	21
22	Installation of V	12	15	23	60	7.7	Yes	17	15
23	Equipped of W	3	3	4	3	1.7	-	-	25

No	Task Name	Optimistic	Mostlikely Time	Pessimistic	Duration (Te)	Variance (V)	Critical	Predecessors	Successors
24	Equipped of X	3	3	7	3	1.7	-	24	29
25	Installation of Y	7	10	12	10	3.2	-	21	-
26	Install of Z	14	15	19	20	4.5	-	20FF	15;30
27	Install ZA	3	4	7	4	2.0	-	-	30
28	Installation of ZB	10	13	15	13	3.6	-	25	-
29	Connection ZC	18	19	22	19	4.4	-	2;20;27;28	-

3.4. Crashing and Cost Slope

Before crashing was done, duration of completing the process of final aircraft assembly was 14 days or 98 hours. In this case, company expected the duration of 2nd Station final assembly to be shortened, as the project should be in concordance with the regulation of the company. So, crashing was performed to shorten the duration into 10 days or 70 hours. Shortly, company needed to perform crashing for 4 days or 28 hours using PERT. To accelerate the project, the company added a regulation relating to overtime for the workers. Besides, information of increasing cost for overtime payment is shown on the Table 2. One of the operation where crashing was performed was the operation that has critical path in the estimation of PERT. The critical path was the path that has the longest duration to be done so that this path could be a reference for the company in shortening the final aircraft assembly at 2nd Station.

Table 2. Cost Slope

No	Task Name	Normal Time (hrs)	Crash time (hrs)	Normal cost (IDR/hrs)	Crash cost (IDR/hrs)	Cost slope (IDR/hrs)
2	Install of B	2	1	60,000	350,000	290,000
7	Instal of G	5	3	150,000	420,000	135,000
9	Install of I	5	3	150,000	420,000	135,000
14	Connection N	15	8	450,000	1,330,000	125,714
16	Install P	2	1	60,000	280,000	220,000
22	Installation of V	60	30	1,800,000	4,410,000	87,000

Based on the critical path result, Table 2 shows the estimation of cost slope, with crash time value that is derived from experts' assessment. The decision to perform crashing was based on the minimum cost at the cost slope, that it was the 22nd activity spending Rp 87,000. The 22nd

activity had the longest duration so that it was considered to be the priority than any other activities. Duration shortening value of the 22nd activity is 30 hours. By performing crashing in 22nd activity, it could fulfill company's expectation to shorten the project up to 28 hours. The total amount of crashing cost was Rp 2.610.000, which is derived from the cost slope thirty-hour downtime at the 22nd activity.

4. Conclusion

The completion of 2nd station final assembly could be done in 14 days or 98 hours. The company made a policy to perform crashing at the 2nd station by considering critical path derived from PERT. Critical path was in the operation 2, 7, 9, 14, 16, and 22, which these operations were taken into consideration for the company when the crashing was performed. Thus, crashing value could be shortened into 10 days out of 14 days, with a probability value of 48.08%. In addition, and for consideration, company that continued to apply crashing on the operation 22 (as the subsequent of critical path) would resulted in the escalation of the cost slope into 4.8%. Meanwhile, the manpower that was used at the 2nd station final assembly process consists of 6 FMI, 2 FAI and 1 XSE. The crashing performing by the company led to cost increase for worker overtime. From cost slope calculation, the total increase in cost at the 22nd activity was Rp 87.000. The cost slope in the 22nd activity was lower than any other activities that were passed by critical path so that the company takes a decision to perform crashing.

The upcoming research can use CPM method. CPM method refers to developing schedule that examines risks, allowances, and availability of resources. By using CPM method, it is expected that it can suggest a novelty for this study.

5. References

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